

Chemical Investigation of *Portulaca quadrifida* Seed

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GLC studies of *Portulaca quadrifida* seed oil along with isolation of hexacosanyl acetate, eicosanic acid, cerotin, palmitic acid, β -sitosterol and β -amyirin from petroleum ether extract with quantitative and qualitative determinations of sugars from aqueous extract of seed have been reported. Besides these, an acyclic long chain aliphatic ester (VI), hitherto unknown in plant kingdom, has also been isolated from the petroleum ether extract.

PORTULACA quadrifida (Portulacaceae) (Hindi-Ram Jata¹, Eng.-Purslane) is a common weed throughout the flora of upper gangetic plain and is common all over India and also in tropical parts of Asia and Africa. It is much used as a pot herb by poorer classes but is occasionally cultivated. We have reported antiimplantation² and antispermatogenic³ effects in *P. quadrifida* along with antifertility effect in another species of the same genus, i.e., *P. oleracea*⁴.

Oil (I) obtained from petroleum ether (60-80°) extract was a brownish yellow oil with the following physico-chemical constants; yield 12.5%; saponification equivalent, 323.5; iodine number, 120.4; total acid value, 5.94; % acetyl value, 3.5 and refractive index, n_D^{20} 1.545. The oil was saponified with 0.5N alcoholic KOH and separated into unsaponified and saponified fractions. The unsaponified fraction was found to contain β -sitosterol. The saponified fraction (Yield, 66.5%; saponification equivalent, 289.2 and iodine number, 143.19) was separated into saturated (Yield 8.75%, m.p. 63°; b.p. 215° and iodine number, 8.56) and unsaturated (Yield 72.91%; b.p. ~219° and iodine number, 127.13) fatty acids following the usual alcohol-lead salt method⁵⁻⁷. GLC studies of methyl esters of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids were carried out separately. The methyl esters⁸ obtained after refluxing the corresponding mixture of acids with methanol in presence of conc. H_2SO_4 were analysed through glc using Silicon QF-1 (5%, 10') column. Individual components of each mixture of methyl esters were identified through retention times and comparing them with standard retention times obtained under the same conditions. Quantitative determinations were made by calculating the area under each peak by triangular method⁹. The retention times of peaks obtained in glc of methyl esters of saturated fatty acids corresponded to methyl myristate (1.94%), methyl palmitate (40.90%), methyl stearate (53.68%) and methyl arachidate (9.28%). The mixture of methyl esters of unsaturated fatty acids was found to have methyl palmitoleate (6.15%), methyl linolenate (0.83%), methyl linoleate (3.72%) and methyl oleate (89.30%).

Further elutions with different solvent systems afforded a white waxy solid II (m.p. 59°), hydrolysis product (m.p. 78°) followed by separation of compounds III (m.p. 76°), methyl (m.p. 54°) and ethyl (m.p. 50°) esters; IV (m.p. 78°), acetyl derivative (m.p. 65°) and V (m.p. 63°) and were identified as hexacosanyl acetate(II), eicosanic acid(III), cerotin (IV) and palmitic acid(V).

Successive elutions obtained with $C_6H_6 - CHCl_3$ (50 : 50) afforded a dirty white solid which on crystallisation from methanol or acetone afforded a white waxy solid(VI) melting at 48°. The compound VI was assigned the molecular formula as $C_{32}H_{64}O_2$ on the basis of elemental and mass spectral data. IR spectrum showed characteristic bands at ν_{max}^{KBr} cm^{-1} , 2930, 2860, 1710, 1465, 1415, 1385 and 725. These peaks are characteristic of an aliphatic long chain ester. UV spectrum in *n*-hexane showed λ_{max} at 213 nm. NMR spectrum of the compound, taken in CCl_4 , displayed two signals (t) of six protons at δ 1.1 and δ 1.17 indicating the presence of two $C - CH_3$ groups. A signal (t) observed at δ 2.38 could be assigned to two protons of $-CH_2 - C -$ group and the signal (t) of two protons

$$\begin{array}{c} \parallel \\ O \\ \parallel \\ -CH_2 - O \end{array}$$

of a $-CH_2 - O$ group was observed at δ 2.48. A sharp and large signal(s) characteristic of a long chain of $-CH_2 -$ group appeared at δ 1.48.

The molecular ion (M^+) peak was observed as a weak peak at m/e 480. Presence of peaks at 466, 452, 438 and 424 showed the presence of *n*-butyl group (C_4H_9). A further loss of a unit 28 was attributed to $-C -$ group. The peaks at m/e 396

$$\begin{array}{c} \parallel \\ O \\ \parallel \\ -C - \end{array}$$

and 397 were assigned to heptacosanol residue. Loss of $C_8H_{16}O_2$ species was indicated by the presence of a peak at m/e 101. A further loss of mass number 18 due to a water molecule was observed by the appearance of a peak at m/e 379. The successive mass fragmentation pattern revealed a uniform loss of mass numbers 14 ($-CH_2 -$ groups)

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upto m/e 43 indicating the presence of an unbranched saturated hydrocarbon chain of 27 carbon atoms.

On the basis of elemental and spectral data the compound VI was assigned the structure and identified as heptacosanyl valerate (heptacosanyl pentanoate).

The fractions obtained on further elutions with CHCl_3 and $\text{CHCl}_3 - \text{CH}_3\text{COOEt}$ (75 : 25) afforded compounds VII (m.p. 136°) and VIII (m.p. 196°) which were identified as β -sitosterol and β -amyrin respectively on the basis of spectral data, co-tlc with standard sample and formation of acetates.

Aqueous extract of the *P. quadrifida* seed gave positive Molisch's test and red precipitates with Fehling's and Benedict's solutions. Paper chromatographic examination revealed the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose. A quantitative examination of sugars of aqueous extract established the percentage of reducing and non-reducing sugars as 2.34 and 11.42 respectively.

Experimental

(A) *Petroleum ether extract*: Oily extract obtained after exhaustive extraction of *P. oleracea* seeds with petroleum ether (60-80°) was chromatographed over deactivated alumina to obtain the following compounds:

Compound	m.p.	Eluent
I (Oil)	—	Petroleum ether
II	59°	Petroleum ether
III	76°	Petroleum ether-benzene (40 : 60)
IV	78°	Petroleum ether-benzene (20 : 80)
V	63°	Benzene
VI	48°	Benzene-chloroform (50 : 50)
VII	136°	Chloroform
VIII	196°	Chloroform-ethyl acetate (75 : 25).

Saponification of Oil(I): A known amount (100 g) of oil (I) was saponified with 0.5 N ethanolic KOH (500 ml) and the hydrolysate was extracted with solvent ether to obtain ether soluble (unsaponified) (i) and ether insoluble or water soluble (saponified) (ii) fractions.

(i) *Unsaponified fraction*: The unsaponified fraction after crystallisation from ethanol gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 136°.

(ii) *Saponified fraction*: The aqueous fraction was hydrolysed with dil. H_2SO_4 to liberate free fatty acids. The acids were extracted with solvent ether filtered and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 followed by filtration and distillation.

Resolution of the mixture into saturated and unsaturated fatty acids⁵⁻⁷: The mixture of fatty acids obtained was separated into saturated and unsaturated acids by following the usual alcohol-lead salt method.

50 g of mixture of fatty acids was taken in 250 ml ethanol, boiled and mixed with a boiling solution of 35 g lead acetate in 250 ml ethanol containing 0.75 ml glacial acetic acid and boiled. The lead salt settled on standing overnight at 15°. After filtration, two parts were obtained: (i) alcohol-insoluble part (lead salts of saturated fatty acids) (4.48 g) and (ii) alcohol-soluble part (lead salts of saturated fatty acids) (40.8 g).

(i) *Alcohol-insoluble part (solid or saturated fatty acids)*: The mixture of insoluble lead salts was dissolved in distilled water decomposed with dil. H_2SO_4 and extracted with solvent ether. The mixture of saturated fatty acids obtained on distillation was stored at 0°.

(ii) *Alcohol-soluble part (liquid or unsaturated fatty acids)*: The mixture of soluble lead salts after distillation of ethanol was dissolved in ether and washed with distilled water. The ethereal solution of lead salts of the acids was washed with dil. H_2SO_4 followed by water. A mixture of liquid fatty acids was obtained after distillation of ether. The mixture of unsaturated fatty acids was stored at 0°.

GLC studies of methyl esters of fatty acids^{8,9}:

The methyl esters of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids were subjected to gas liquid chromatography separately.

Preparation of methyl esters of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids:

Saturated (5 g) and unsaturated (60 g) fatty acids were refluxed in separate round bottom flasks with calculated amounts of methanol (25 and 300 ml respectively) containing 1.5% by weight of conc. H_2SO_4 for one hr. After cooling, the esters were extracted with ether, washed with water and dried after distilling off the solvent.

The gas liquid chromatograms of methyl esters of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids were recorded separately on Silicon-QF-1 (5%, 10') column with the following parameters: solvent, solvent ether; detector temperature, 200° (saturated) and 230° (unsaturated); gas, hydrogen; flow, 50 ml/min; current; 200 ma; chart speed, 30"/hr and sample size, 1.5 μ l.

Hydrolysis of compound II: 20 mg of acetate was hydrolysed by refluxing with 5% ethanolic KOH (5ml) for 30 minutes on water bath, cooled and extracted with solvent ether. The ethereal solution after distillation yielded a dirty white solid which was crystallised from acetone-ether mixture to give a colourless compound, m.p. 78°. It was identified as hexacosanol on the basis of spectral analysis, m.m.p. and co-tlc with authentic sample.

Compound III:

(i) *Methyl ester*: Methyl ester of the acid(III) was prepared by refluxing 20 mg of acid with 2 ml of methanol containing 0.2 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 . The hydrolysate, after cooling the mixture, was extracted with solvent ether and washed with water and 10% KOH respectively and dried (Na_2SO_4).

The solid recovered after distillation of solvent was crystallised from ethanol when a white solid melting at 54° was obtained.

(ii) *Ethyl ester* : 25 mg acid was refluxed with 2 ml of ethanol containing 0.2 ml of conc. H₂SO₄. The experimental details described in the preparation of methyl esters were followed thereafter. The ethyl ester was crystallised from ethanol to obtain a colourless solid with melting point 50°.

Acetylation of compound IV : 10 mg of compound (IV) was refluxed with 0.2 ml of acetic anhydride and 0.2 ml of dry pyridine for 1 hr. The acetyl derivative was crystallised from ethanol as colourless plates, m.p. 64°.

(B) *Aqueous extract* : The crushed seeds were extracted with distilled water for about 5 hrs, filtered and cooled. The aqueous extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and preliminary tests were performed.

The aqueous extract responded positive to Molisch's test and gave a red precipitate with Fehling's and Benedict's solutions indicating the presence of reducing sugars. Sugars in aqueous extract were analysed by paper chromatography on Whatman No. 1 in the solvent systems (a) *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (upper phase) (40 : 10 : 50) ; (b) *n*-butanol-ethanol-water (50 : 10 : 40) ; (c) butanol-ethanol-water-ammonia (45 : 5 : 49 : 1) ; (d) *n*-butanol-ammonia (99 : 1) and (e) methylethylketone-ammonia (99 : 1) using aniline hydrogen phthalate as spraying reagent. The analysis revealed presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose

in the aqueous extract on comparing the R_f values with authentic samples.

*Estimations of sugars*¹⁰ : 20 g of crushed seeds were exhaustively extracted with distilled water and the final volume was made up to 500 ml. Estimations of sugars were done by titration with Fehling's solution.

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